

ADJUSTING THE QUALITY OF TEXTILE PRODUCTS TO INTERNATIONAL STANDARD

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Аннотация:

Ушбу тезисда мамлакатимиз пахта хом ашёни чуқур қайта ишлашга қаратилган кластер тизимида фаолият юритаётган корхоналар томонидан ишлаб чиқарилаётган маҳсулотларга халқаро стандартларни жорий этилиши шунингдек экспорт географиясини кенгайтиришда хорижий мамлакатлар томонидан талаб этиладиган сертификацияларини жорий этиш каби масалалар жой олган.

Калит сўзлар:

Замонавий технология, модернизация, қўшимча қиймат, экспорт хажми, халқаро стандарт, халқаро коалитса, рақобатбардошлик, сифат менежменти, инвестиция, меҳнат унумдорлиги, инновацион салоҳият.

Аннотация:

В данном дипломной работе рассматриваются такие вопросы, как внедрение международных стандартов в продукцию, выпускаемую предприятиями, работающими в кластерной системе, направленной на глубокую переработку хлопкового сырья нашей страны, а также внедрение сертификации, требуемой зарубежными странами при расширении география экспорта.

Ключевые слова:

Современные технологии, модернизация, добавленная стоимость, объем экспорта, международный стандарт, международная коалитса,

конкурентоспособность, управление качеством, инвестиции, производительность труда, инновационный потенциал.

Abstract:

In this thesis, issues such as the introduction of international standards to the products produced by the enterprises operating in the cluster system aimed at the deep processing of cotton raw materials of our country, as well as the introduction of certifications required by foreign countries in expanding the export geography, are included.

Key words:

Modern technologies, modernization, added value, export volume, international standard, international coalition, competitiveness, quality management, investment, labor productivity, innovative potential.

Мавзуга оид адабиётлар таҳлили

Several proposals of scientists have been put forward to increase the economic and export potential of textile clusters. Our local scientists A.Soliev and Z.Khakimov's articles "Cluster theory and the possibilities of using the experience of the countries applying it in practice in the Namangan region".[1] The reason for the selection of these scientists in this area is the high volume of production of ready-made products of the region.

A.SH.Bekmurodov and Yang Song Be in the monograph entitled "Cluster approach in the development of the strategy of the textile industry of Uzbekistan".[2] ministerial and practical approaches to the cluster, the nature of the cluster in increasing product competitiveness, the results achieved in the processing of raw materials and foreign countries, companies and products illustrated by examples. Also a number of proposals on the use of these foreign experiences in the Republic have been presented.

American scientists M.Porter “Theory of competitive style” [3], M.Enright, S.Resenfeld, P.Maskell and M.Lorentsen “the concept of regional clusters” [4], A.Marshall “Theory of industrial zones” [5], P.Becatin put forward “Theories of Italian industrial enterprises”.[6] According to T.Kono, if the type of products produced by the enterprise is limited to only one type of product, then such an enterprise is limited to the production of other types of products, so it is classified as a single specialized enterprise.

On the contrary, if different types of products are produced, such an enterprise is considered a diversified enterprise. Depending on the formation of market relations, the enterprise is limited to diversification or production of one type of product.[7] R.Pitts and H.Hopkins, following a slightly different aspect, define diversification as conducting several types of business at the same time.[8] In the above-mentioned theories of foreign scientist, it is emphasized that clusters are a system that combines the activities of educational, scientific, technological, economic and other service entities, which are considered highly effective in realizing competitive advantage.

Professor Michael Porter of Harvard University emphasized the development of the industry of economically developed countries and the development of advanced industrial sectors in the world in his scientific research studies. [9]

According to theory of I.Ansoff, diversification is a term applied to the process of redistribution of resources available in a particular enterprise to other areas of activity. It is related to the possibility of transition to new technologies, access to new markets and access to new industries, while increasing production capacity. [10]

Cluster theory was also studied by Russian scientists Yu.S.Artmonova, B.B.Khurustalev [11], and projects on its implementation were developed. The creation of the above theories and their practical importance imply increasing the competitiveness of the economy of countries, sectors and enterprises and achieving high efficiency.

The entry of local textile products into foreign markets, in order to find their place in the international competitive environment, is determined by the conformity of the products with the requirements of the international standard and the reforms in personnel policy. It is known that since 2017 fundamental reforms have been carried out in the textile sector in our country.

This includes providing textile enterprises with modern technologies, providing them with low-interest credit funds for their modernization, providing enterprises with working capital, creating additional value through the deep processing chain, and at the same time establishing trade and economic relations with foreign countries to expand the volume and geography of exports. Important strategic tasks are being implemented. If we consider the above-mentioned as a factor, in the implementation of these factors and increasing the volume of exports, the issue of personnel, compliance of products with international standard requirements and, of course, transport-logistics services in the transportation of finished products are of great importance.

Today, after the removal of the cotton boycott from our country by the international Coalition, relations with various international companies are being strengthened to enter the markets of the new region. As an example, the GSP+system is considered as a system that ensures the sale of finished products to EU countries. This system provides tariff preferences for certain types of products from developed countries to developing countries. It is known that there are 29 European Union countries with a total population of more than 500 million people. They mainly import products made from environmentally friendly raw materials. This in itself determines the competitiveness of our country to the requirements of European standards.

Standards are effective tools capable of driving innovation and improving productivity. They can make companies more successful, simplify, secure and make people's everyday lives healthier. Also with help of standards, environmental sustainability and social responsibility, which have become the main requirements

for entering the EU and US markets, are ensured in the production of textile products.

Figure-1

Adjusting the indicators quality of textile products to international standards in the republic of Uzbekistan.

Source: Prepared based on the information of the “Uztextile” association.

The importance of international standards in the field of textiles is immeasurable. They play an important role not only in improving product quality and entering the world market, but also in increasing productivity. In the textile sector of our country, with the support of the “Uztextile” association, active work is being carried out on the introduction of international standards, including cooperation with leading international organizations and companies to ensure the compliance of national textile enterprises and the products they produce with world standards.

It should be noted that the boycott of Uzbek cotton by the Cotton Campaign coalition was canceled due to the consistent implementation of the international standards system in the republic, which is the biggest achievement in 2022.

According to statistics, today the international standards ISO 9001/14001/18001/45001/50001, OEKO TEX-100, SEDEX-30, BSCI-25, GOTS

and Organic EU-8, OCS-4, CE marketing-3, GRS-one was introduced by the enterprise.

Network enterprises follow the principles of ESG in addition to ISO quality management standards. In a broad sense, this is a sustainable development of commercial activity, a responsible attitude to the environment (E-environment); high social responsibility (S-social); based on principles such as high quality of corporate management (G-governance). In its modern form, ESG-principles were expressed by former UN Secretary General Kofi Annan. He suggested that the managers of the world's largest companies should incorporate these principles into their strategies to combat climate change in the first place.

Environment principles show how much the company cares about the environment and how it tries to reduce the damage it causes to the environment. Social principles express the company's attitude towards employees, suppliers, customers, partners and consumers. In order to comply with the standards, businesses must work on the quality of working conditions, monitor gender balance and invest in social projects. Management principles apply to the quality of enterprise management: These include transparency of reporting and management salaries, healthy workplace environment, shareholder relations and anti-corruption measures. A company that adheres to ESG principles gains a number of advantages, such as higher attractiveness and financial indicators, better labor productivity from investors and financial institutions. In the long term, following the principles of ESG will increase business reputation and create a positive image of the company, reduce the costs of environment taxes and increase the technological and innovative potential of the business.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan's textile sector has a chance to prosper in the international market by raising the quality of its products to meet international standards. However, this offers a complex issue. We have examined several facets of this undertaking during this study, taking into account the industry's current status, difficulties faced, and tactics used to adhere to international standards.

The textile sector in Uzbekistan has a strong history and a lot of untapped potential thanks to a trained labor population and ideal growing and textile-making conditions for cotton. But in order to take advantage of these benefits and effectively compete in global markets, Uzbek textile producers must ensure that their goods meet the strict quality requirements set forth by authorities and consumers around the world.

List of literature

1.A.Soliev and Z.Khakimov “Possibilities of using the cluster theory and the experience of the countries applying it in practice in the Namangan region” “Biznes-ekspert” magazine, issue1, 2014, pp.52-57.

2.A.SH.Bekmurodov and Yang Song Be “Cluster approach in the development of the strategy of the textile industry of Uzbekistan”.Monograph,2006, 112 pages.

3.Porter M. International competition.-M.: International relations,1993. P-51.

4. Enright, M (1996) “Regional Clustersand Economic Development: A.Research Agenda”, in Staber, U.,Schaefer, N. And Sharma, B, (Eds). “Business Networks: Prospects for Regional Development, Berlin”. Walter de Gruyter, p.190-213.

5.Marshall A. Principles of Economic Science, I-III.Per.from English-M.-Publishing Group “Progress”, 1993.

6. Becattini G. From Marshalls to the Italian “Industrial Districts”/www.copetitivness.org.

7.Kono T.Strategy and structure of Japanese enterprises.-M.:Mysl,1987.-214 p.

8.Novitskiy E.G. Problems of strategic management of diversified corporations M.Bukvitsa, 2001.

9. Porter M.E. On Competition. Boston: Harvard Business School Press, 1998.

10. Ansoff I., Mc Donell E. Implanting strategic management. Prentice Hall, 1990-568 p.

11. Clusters policies and cluster initiatives: theory, methodology, practice. (Collective monograph). Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, Ministry of Economic Development of the Russian Federation, Government of the Penza Region. Penza-2013.